

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B404
 Date: 23/09/08
 Take Off: 08:56:50
 Landing: 12:06:48
 Flight Time 3h 09m 58s

Campaign: ADIENT/CAVIAR

Operating Area: SW Approaches

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Luc Lathouwers	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight	
3	CCM1	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist	Ellie Highwood	Reading	
5	Flight Manager	Steve Devereau	FAAM	
6	Core Chem / AVAPS / CCM2	Doug Anderson	FAAM	
7	Cloud Physics	Phil Rosenberg	FAAM	
8	ARIES	Stuart Newman	Met Office	
9	SWS / SHIMS	Debbie O'Sullivan	Met Office	
10	Wet Neph / PSAP	Andy Wilson	Met Office	
11	CVI / FWVS	Jeff Norwood-Brown	Met Office	
12	TAFTS	Ralph Beeby	Imperial College	
13	MARSS / DEIMOS	Dave Pollard	Met Office	
14	Mission Scientist 2	Megan Northway	Reading University	
15	Mission Scientist Training	Grant Allen	Manchester University	
16	AMS / SP2	Gavin McMeeking	Manchester University	
17				
18				

Flight Track:

B404 Track 23-SEP-08

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B404

Date: 23rd September 2008

Project: ADIENT/CAVIAR

Location: SW Approaches, Southern Irish Sea

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
070613		!	0.00 kft	306	O3 zero started
071537		!	0.00 kft	306	Nevzorov zero
084027		Start-Up	0.00 kft	127	engine start
084634		!	0.00 kft	126	start taxi
085650		T/O	0.98 kft	032	Cranfield
090034		event	6.8 kft	050	Nevzorov/JW zero
090059		!	7.2 kft	082	retract BBR cover
090447		!	10.0 kft	242	Nevzorov/JW zero
090741		!	10.0 kft	243	Heimann cal
093045	094508	Profile 1.1	18.0 - 3.7 kft	255	
093212		!	16.7 kft	254	extend BBR cover
094706	095007	Profile 1.1	3.7 - 1.7 kft	115	
095148	095455	Profile 1.1	1.7 - 0.5 kft	303	
095502	100522	Run 1.1	0.50 kft	310	
095806		!	0.50 kft	329	retract BBR cover
095913		!	0.50 kft	330	Nevzorov/JW zero
100237		!	0.50 kft	333	Heimann cal
100630		!	0.50 kft	093	
100726	103642	Run 1.2	0.50 kft	183	
103227		!	0.50 kft	107	Heimann cal
103642	103739	Profile 2.1	0.50 - 0.05 kft	194	
103758	104134	Run 2.1	0.10 kft	205	
104143	104655	Profile 3.1	0.10 - 1.4 kft	197	
104337		!	0.89 kft	195	Nevzorov/JW zero
104413		!	1.3 kft	188	overhead Camborne
104656	105057	Profile 4.1	1.4 - 0.05 kft	192	
105243	105615	Run 3.1	0.50 kft	000	
105627	105833	Profile 5.1	0.50 - 1.6 kft	012	
105841	110051	Run 4.1	1.5 kft	017	
110052	110319	Profile 6.1	1.5 - 0.50 kft	008	
110325	110940	Run 5.1	0.50 kft	026	
110820		!	0.50 kft	032	Heimann cal
110948	111028	Profile 7.1	0.50 - 0.05 kft	004	
111045	111908	Profile 8.1	0.05 - 5.0 kft	009	
111313		!	1.1 kft	004	Nevzorov/JW zero
120648		Land	0.00 kft	285	Cranfield

B404 Track 23-SEP-08

ADIENT Flight B404: EU plume in Bay of Biscay

FAAM Sortie Brief

Tuesday, September 23, 2008

Operating areas: EUCAARI Waypoints H2 to H6 on 5W line preferably or similar points on 7/8W line if 5W depending on airspace options.

Weather: No rainfall. Northeasterly/easterly conditions. Preferably cloud free

Sortie Summary: In-situ sampling and (if cloud free) radiation work in large aerosol plume forecast from continental Europe in Bay of Biscay. Transit at medium or high level to Berry Head or Culdrose followed by descent in the English Channel area. Low level (500ft) in-situ sampling along longitude line, lingering somewhere on route to do radiation work if cloud free. Land to refuel in Spain and transit return to Cranfield.

Flight Patterns:

- 1) If clear skies at Cranfield (no clouds to interfere with direct radiation) prior to take-off perform pirouette on the runway. (360 degree turn, at around 120 degrees per minute).
- 2) Take off Cranfield 10:30 L (9:30z) and transit at mid/high level to Berry Head/Culdrose ([50 mins, T=50 mins]
- 3) Profile descent in English Channel area at 1000 ft/ min above 3000 ft and 500 ft/min below 3000 ft to 500ft or minimum altitude [20 min, T=70]
- 4) Ascend to max aerosol layer (500 - 2000 ft) and perform an SLR down 5W to EUCAARI point H5 (46N, 5W) [45 mins, T=115]
- 5) **If cloud free** perform radiation module between points H5 and H6(45N, 5W) as follows
 - 5a) Profile descent to minimum altitude at 500ft per minute towards H6 then profile ascent to 5000ft or above aerosol, continuing towards H6. (H5-H6 at low level= 15mins)
 - 5b) On reaching H6; procedural turn onto reciprocal heading and SLR above aerosol to H5
 - 5c) Perform 2 orbits at solar zen +10 degrees above H5
 - 5d) Procedural turn onto heading to H6. Descend to within aerosol layer towards H6
 - 5e) At H6 procedural turn and perform 15 min SLR within aerosol to H5
 - 5f) At H5 broken profile descent to minimum altitude below aerosol for 2 sets of 2 orbits at solar zen+10
 - 5g) Turn towards H6 and descend to 100ft. 15 min SLR at 100ft to point H6 [100mins, T=215]
- 6) **If not cloud free**, perform profile ascent to FL100 to assess aerosol profile in Biscay region. Perform a series of SLRs within aerosol layer or layers along line 5W
- 7) Return to 500ft and continue down 5W south of H6 within aerosol layer as far as possible
- 8) Profile ascent as necessary to join flight pattern for landing and refueling
- 9) Land/Refuel- where? [300mins]
- 10) Take/off, Transit to Cranfield

ADIANT Flight B404 Debrief

Tuesday 23rd September 2008 – Ellie Highwood

Sortie location: Irish Sea and Bristol Channel; Camborne.

Sortie aim: Large-scale plume transformation and radiation work in the Bristol Channel and West of Wales. CAVIAR work over Camborne. Validation of model aerosol forecasts in a case where the UK 4km and NAE models differed substantially in terms of strength and extent of aerosol plume from UK.

Weather encountered: Dry. Patchy low and mid level cloud in Bristol Channel and Irish Sea. Rain and more extensive cloud near Cranfield.

Sortie Summary:

Take-off from Cranfield was under extensive low and mid-level cloud cover. Low cloud was between 1300ft and 3700ft. During transit to AMPEP Waypoint 49 the low and midlevel cloud became more broken and high level cloud disappeared. A broken profile descent was performed in the Bristol Channel area under largely clear skies. Small amounts of StCu meant no radiation work. More importantly the air appeared very clean. Neph. Counts were 15m^{-1} all the way to the surface. Sea state slight with few white caps. Low level runs at 500ft above the ocean were performed to 52N, 6W. Little scattering was evident. A further SLR at 500ft was performed down the 6W line to 51N. Some increase in scattering was apparent towards the end of this run. Cloud remained patchy and increased towards the south. Some possible nucleation events were seen, and some changes in the wavelength dependency of the scattering were observed. SMPS showed a peak at 90nm. Given the paucity of aerosol, it was decided to continue at low level towards the Camborne area. Towards Camborne (102326 and onwards) more aerosol was observed with scattering up to $\sim 50\text{m}^{-1}$. A peak in NO_x was observed to be anticorrelated with ozone concentrations. PCASP and CCN showed some changes in size and amount of particles. AMS detected some sulphate and organics. A descent to 50ft was followed by a run at 100ft towards the coast at Camborne, climbing to 2000ft to pass over land and returning to 100ft over the ocean to the south of Cornwall. Cloud was extensively patchy and Camborne reported not being able to make measurements. Therefore a return run over the Cornish Peninsula was performed at 500ft for in-situ sampling of the somewhat elevated aerosol amounts. A profile ascent to 5000ft was performed in the Bristol Channel at the location of the previously observed peak in aerosol. However, substantial amounts of aerosol were not found during this ascent (cloud base at 2600ft) and the air was clean above (no evidence of long range pollutant transport at altitude). The flight was therefore called off at this point and the profile continued for transit at mid level to Cranfield. On landing at Cranfield cloud cover remained overcast, with light rain.

Mission Scientist's Log

DigiMemo e-Page

Flight No **B.404** Date 23/9/08 Name E. Highland Page 1 of 4

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
084500	pre T/O			Cranfield	8/8 low/mid cld T=13° light winds Td 10-21. Rain Drizzle
085300	T/O				Cloud @ 1300ft → 3700 clear slot cloud layer @
090504					St Cu broken but extensive Cloud extensive above & below high/mid cloud decreasing towards west. RH dropping @ 10000 FLO10
091138	Transit	FLO10	244		Mid cloud & low cloud 7/8 Very thin Ci above, & ahead Semi persistent contrails above
091924		FL180	259		
093016	S136,312	FL180			
093046	P1.1	FL180↓			Large patches of low cloud extensive Some mid cloud & high cloud.
093918		FLD10↓			Mid level cloud extensive
094136					Low cloud only scattered in Bristol Channel. Pt 49 Clear
094358		FLO50↓	297		Large ship Profile Broken
094508	P1.1	FLO50			Restart profile
094706	P1.1	FLO50	116		mid/low patches to South, clearer to North.
094817	P1.1				Change to 500ft/min
095008	P1.1	2000ft			low cloud patchy at 2000ft P interrupt

Mission Scientist's Log

DigiMemo e-Page

Flight No **B404** Date **23/9/08** Name **E. Highwood** Page **2** of **4**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
09 51 36	P1.1	2000ft			Recommence descent
					15 m ⁻¹ on neph! Clear
09 54 50	P1.1	500ft			End profile
09 54 50	R1	500ft	321		Clear! Some white caps
10 05 26	R1	500ft			End run Visibility good (to Ireland)
10 07 20	R2	500ft	183		Clear, scattered low cloud SHIPS peak @ 90nm.
					Not much of anything
					Some nucleation events
10 23 26	R2	500ft	117	Turn	more aerosol Turn towards
					Peak in last few minutes of R2 before turn
					PCASP, CCN
10 31 19	R2	500ft	109		Cloud more extensive low/mid
					Aerosol clearing → 40 m ⁻¹
					PSAP recording problems
					Web neph problems
10 35 20					Change in size distribution to larger sizes
					NO _x ↑, O ₃ ↓ Cloudy patchy
10 36 08	R2	500ft			Turn
10 36 08	P2.1		194		Descent to 50 ft some whitecaps
10 36	R3	100ft			Visibility good.
10 41 43	R3	End 100ft			End of run, start climb over land
	P3.1	100ft ↑			Scattered low cloud & mid + cirrus

Mission Scientist's Log

DigiMemo e-Page

Flight No **B.404** Date **23/9** Name **E. Highwood** Page **3** of **4**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
104708		2000ft			Camborne patchy low cloud Across higher Cloud base
104655	P4.1	2000ft ↓			500 ft/min
104928	P4				Boat!
101557	P4.1	300ft			End profile
105244	R3.1	500ft	2		Start run from Scout back across Camborne
105626	R3.1 P5.1	500ft			End /start climb to cross Cornwall
105831	P5.1 R4.1	2000ft			Over Cornwall, scattered cloud at all level. Visibility good Cloud just above us
110052	R4.1 P6.1	2000ft ↓	22		descending north of Cornwall to 500ft
110318	P6.1 R5.1	500ft →	22		Few whitecaps. Patchy cloud at many levels
110940	R5.1 P7.1	500ft ↓	5		
111045	P8.1	50ft ↑	5		
111417	P8.1	↑1600ft			cloud cloud 2600ft
111752		3000ft 3700ft			Change ascent rate, in cloud clean, cloud above.
111908	P8.1	5000ft			End profile END SCIENCE, climb to home.

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B404

Date: 23/09/08 Operator:PDR DRS time: DAU1 time: DAU2 time: DAU3 time: AUX1 time: AUX2 time: Page 1 of 2
 PcasP vref 7.2, flow rate 8.2, ffssp vref 3.4, 2dc end element voltages 1.25/1.55

G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/c	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
																2dp not run due to noise problem	
																2dc cleaned	
08:59:17	100															Drop from 250 counts	
9:02:15	10																
																Start profile 1.1	
09:42:30	100		175													Reentered boundary layer	
09:49:00	300		176													FI22	
09:51:00	450		176													FI 16	
																End profile 1.1	
																Start run 1.1	
09:56:00	300															Peak in pcasp to 1500 /cc at 09:54:50	
10:02:00	200		179														
																End run 1.1	
																Start run 1.2	
10:07:30	200		180														
10:19:00	250		184														
10:21:00	500		185														
10:25:00	350		186														
10:31:00	450		188														
10:35:30	500		189													Peak now seen at ~300nm on pcasp spectrum	
																End run 1.2	
																Start profile 2.1	
10:37:35	500		189													50 ft	
																End run 2.1	
																Start run 2.1	
																End run 2.1	
																Start profile 3.1	
10:43:00	400		191														
10:45:00	500		191														
10:51:00	400		192													50ft	
																Start run 3.1	
10:53:00	400		193														
																End run 3.1	
																Start profile 5.1	
10:57:00	400		194														
																End profile 5.1	
																Start run 4.1	
10:59:00	550		194														
																End run 4.1	
																Start profile 6.1	
11:02:30	500		195														
																End profile 6.1	
																Start run 5.1	
11:03:30	500		196														
																End run 5.1	
																Start profile 7.1	

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B404 **T/O:** 08:56:50
Date of flight: 23/09/08 **Land:** 12:06:48

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		DONE IN EXETER
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B404
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B) 2D PROCESSING		REPROCESS +1hr
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC	Y	
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)	Y	
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	Y	8895 blocks
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) Unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip	Y	Size of Bnnn.dat = 93491
6) FLOODS> WAVE WAVE> CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat WAVE> exit	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section Blocks read = 26830 Blocks written = 26830 Bad reads = 0
7) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 5 min)</i> f) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land + 5 min)</i> g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data: Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N	Y	Start = 085000 End = 121000 Ignore error message scroll (vestigial error from tapes) Are FRW, FSP, IMB, PCA,SEC files in PMSDATA? Y Are they non-zero in size? Y
8) FLOODS> WAVE i). WAVE> imagedisplay a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) File generation no: 0 d) Time from IWC plot: N e) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP f) Start time: <i>As in 7e above</i> g) End time: <i>As in 7f above</i> h) Time interval (sec): 5 recommended (0 for all images) ii). WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 1 min)</i> e) Enter end time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 1 min)</i> f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks: 10 iii). WAVE> exit to create files iv). FTP ascii *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC v). Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter vi). Output as pdf file (720 dpi resolution), appending name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files	Y	2D image display and printing Must be done from FLOODS itself. Note any problems with images 2dc noisy but some images. No 2dp Prepare imagery for Core data From own PC again Start = End = FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_ Bnnn_2Dx-images.ps Notes on this in instructions 4 pages 2dc

<p>9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_tas g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>	Y	<p>NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful.</p> <p>X = b404_tas</p> <p>Start = 085000 End = 121000</p> <p>Time data processed to = 120529 2dproc files present? Y *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat</p>
<p>10) FLOODS> WAVE</p> <p>i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit</p>	Y	<p>Use PVWAVE for this section</p> <p>Error message about HDDR file should be ignored.</p> <p>Records = 126</p>
<p>11) FLOODS> MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>	Y	<p>X = b404_tas Y = (X+1) = b404_tas_2d</p>
<p>12) CHECKS:</p> <p>Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i></p>	N	<p>Use flight_plot to check data is present in mfd file? Y</p>

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B404
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C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	Y	
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. (1.15ccs⁻¹ Feb 07)</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>	Y	Min size = 1 Vol flow rate = 0.82
3) FLOODS> WAVE i).WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' ii). WAVE> exit	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d_pcasp d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>	Y	X = b404_tas_2d Y = X+1 = _tas_2d_pcasp
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and JW peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph – total blue scatter.</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>	N	Is data present in mfd? Use flight_plot to check.

ARIES flight log

Flight: B404

page 1 of 1

Date: 23/9/08

Operator(s): S. NEWMAN

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: ADIENT/CAVIAR, SW Approaches and Bristol Channel

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
							Replaced ARIES-CDM with older version 1-0-7 as test
074458	Pre-flight	6.Z30s	-	0	71	31	abort 074620 (wrong flight name)
074841		6.Z30s	-	0	71	30	Screen brightness temperatures are sensible (unlike yesterday)
							075100 abort
075256		9.N30s	-	0	71	31	BTs look ok
							Abort 075502
							Revert to newest 1-0-10 version of ARIES-CDM
091300	Transit	10.NZ30s	-	0	71	35	Screen brightness temps now wrong (< 3K), radiances ~ -3 $\text{Wcm}^{-2}\text{sr}^{-1}(\text{cm}^{-1})$
							092519 abort
							over Sc below, clear above 0925
095518	R1.1	10.NZ30s	-	0	70	31	Low level over sea, looks clear above
							Abort 100604 in turn
100718	R1.2	10.NZ30s	-	0	71	31	Some cloud to starboard, but fairly clear above
							1010 coming under cloud, patchy
							1021 looks fairly clear
							102330 turning Abort 102421
103800		10.NZ30s	-	0	71	31	100ft run, some patchy Cu above
							104141 abort
104409		10.NZ30s	-	0	71	31	Start overhead Camburn
							Cloud at our level and above
							104606 abort
105838	R4.1	10.NZ30s	-	0	71	31	Cloud above, few clear patches
							Abort 110055
							1121 flight curtailed, heading home

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	23/09/08	Flight	B404	log pages	3
Operator(s)	Pollard		Campaign	ADIENT/CAVIAR			
Departure	Cranfield		Arrival	Cranfield			

System start MARSS

Visual pod inspection							X
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers							X
Close all MARSS circuit breakers							X
FERA on				at time	06:47		
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	16.3	Ch	16.2	Ch18	15.8	
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C	
MARSS CPU on				at time	06:48		
Initial target temperatures	Hot	287.8	Cold	285.5			
Target heating							X
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***							X
Scanning on (LMD box)				at time	07:50		
Scan indication			Monitor)	Visual		X

Deimos

Deimos Orientation (Nadir or Zenith)							Z
Close all Deimos circuit breakers							X
Turn on Deimos CPU							X
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***							X
Start Deimos Software				at time	06:51		
Initial target temperatures	Hot	287.6	Cold	286.4			
Target heating							X
Scan indication			Monitor)	Visual		X
Weather	Cloud		Precip				
	Surface		Pressure				
	Other						

System functionality check (after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$	0	at time	09:06		
Brightness temps 'sensible'						
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	344.39	Cold	281.89	
	Deimos:	Hot	344.35	Cold	292.83	
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B		
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)		
	55.8	16.4	56.4	15.9		
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20	
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)	
	39.25	33.08	39.33	40.98	42.72	

Power changeover

Headset on before start		
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.	
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)		
Exit Deimos Software (x)		
POWER CHANGEOVER		
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton	
Restart Deimos Software		
System running again		at time

Flight #	B404	Date	23/09/08	Operator(s)	Pollard	log page	3	of	3
<i>Time</i>	Run id	Alt/FL	<i>Remarks</i>				Sys		

Data Processing Log			Initials	Date
Flight data copied from MARSS/Deimos PC flash disk to Martian C:\Bxxx\			DP	23/09/08
Check disc space on flash disk (need >~10 MB free)			DP	23/09/08
Copy* Martian logged data from to C:\Bxxx\			DP	23/09/08
Wave processing run and BT files generated			DP	14/11/08
DQM file generated and uploaded			DP	14/11/08
NetCDF file generated and uploaded			DP	14/11/08
C:\Bxxx\ copied to USB drive or CD			DP	23/09/08
Data processing issues/notes:				

Flight:

B404

KEY

Not Fitted

Fitted, Not Operated

Duff Data

Minor Problems

OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nevzorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Fax machine:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H:

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP (fuselage):

CDP (Canister):

CIP 100:

CIP 25:

CPI:

CVI:

SID1:

SID2:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC 3025 (AMS):

INC:

VACC:

CPC 3010A (CVI):

SP2:

UHSAS:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR:

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B404

Date: 23/09/08

Instruments

1. CCN made 6 measurements then 'parameter incorrect' error message
2. Wet Neph PC locked up and was reset around 0955. Wet neph software restored at 1022 but PC would then not see PSAP. Horace PSAP link OK.
3. AMS heater switch turned off by accident during low level flight
4. 2DP not run because of noise problems
5. FWVS not working
6. TAFTS - helium loss
7. SWS near IR module problem
8. SHIMS
9. lower SHIMS not working correctly
10. Question-mark over Nox levels

Aircraft

ISDN Emails

Three sessions for sat picture download

MPDS

Tested during flight - FAAM

Satcom-H Calls

One to Ops Manager

Issues

Nil

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: *23 SEP 08*

Flight No: **B** *404*

Pre-Flighter: *[Signature]*

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect spanners for core chem	
<u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u>				
2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	<i>NO CO - NO GASES</i>
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	<i>no CO - no flow!</i>
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Aft CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fore CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Recording data	
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
12	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
13	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
14	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video Laptop	Checked onboard	
16	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	FWWS	Set up & check on AUTO	<i>NO AUTO mode oblique</i>
17	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked then OFF	
18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC	Fitted & signals checked	
20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Balance checked then back to DP	
21	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GPS (XR5M)	Checked	
22	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom C	Checked	
23	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	<i>video tape now not used</i>

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
24	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	In cockpit
25	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CNC	Butanol filled	
26	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	
27	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PSAP	Pre-flight log actions complete	<i>OBR operating</i>
28	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CGPS	CBs and PC ON	<i>not filled</i>
<u>External Checks</u>				
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
30	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
39	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	All other covers	Removed	
40	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butanol**
41	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42	<input type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				<u>Signed</u>
44	<input type="checkbox"/>	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		
45	<input type="checkbox"/>	ICEX applied		
46	<input type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -		a)Nil b)1-2 drops c)1/4 full or more
47	<input type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe - Traps dried and resealed		

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B404:

Log	Reason
Mission Scientist 2	no log appears to have been taken
Mission Scientist 3	no log appears to have been taken
AVAPS log	No sondes appear to have been dropped on B404
Wet Neph	No log sheet has been provided so far for this flight
CVI	No log sheet has been provided so far for this flight
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	No In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP log	Fit Man notes not operated but Andy Wilson down to operate. Probably no log taken.
CPI log	CPI operator does not create a log sheet
AMS / SP2 log	AMS / SP2 operator does not create a log sheet
TAFTS	TAFTS operator does not create a log sheet
Dry Neph	Operator does not create a log sheet

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	10 Sep 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

The following video recordings in avi format should be available at the BADC :

faam-video-dfc_faam_20080923_r0_b404_104217_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080923_r0_b404_114217_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20080923_r0_b404_084206_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080923_r0_b404_094206_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080923_r0_b404_104206_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080923_r0_b404_114206_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20080923_r0_b404_084206_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080923_r0_b404_094206_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080923_r0_b404_104206_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080923_r0_b404_114206_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20080923_r0_b404_084213_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080923_r0_b404_094213_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080923_r0_b404_104213_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080923_r0_b404_114213_1hz.avi

Missing video recordings:

faam-video-dfc_faam_20080923_r0_b404_094209_1hz failed at Convert I Frame 3600 (final frame)
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080923_r0_b404_084217_1hz failed at Convert I Frame 3
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080923_r0_b404_094217_1hz failed at Convert I Frame 521

No Digital8 video recordings were made on this flight.